

Standards-of-Practice for in situ networks and data-intensive monitoring devices

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List of Acronyms

ADCP	Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler
CDOM	Coloured Dissolved Organic Matter
CTD	Conductivity-Temperature-Depth sensor
FRM	Fiducial Reference Measurement
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GNSS, GPS (D-GPS, RTK GPS)	Global Navigation Satellite System , Global Positioning System, Differential GPS, Real Time Kinematics GPS)
ISAR	Infrared Sea surface temperature Autonomous Radiometer
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
PAR	Photosynthetically Active Radiation
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SI	System of units
SISTeR	Scanning Infrared Sea surface Temperature Radiometer.
SOS	Sensor Observation Service
STA	SensorThings API
WFS	Web Feature Service
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

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1 Executive Summary

This report compiles high-level requirements and opportunities to align in situ data collection with the needs of satellite product and model calibration and validation (‘cal/val’) across the aquatic domain. There is a need for such guidance because, on the one hand, satellite observation benefits from unprecedented and operational observation capabilities, whilst lack of in situ validation datasets are relatively sparse and repeatedly brought up as information gaps and source of product uncertainty. On the other hand, in situ observation communities are relatively fragmented and tend to be self-organised. Coordinating frameworks exist in some domains (predominantly hydrology) but are absent or not yet mature, in other areas.

The satellite observation domains which are considered are water level, extent and volume, temperature, and biogeochemical properties and processes. Here, we define “observation networks” as nodes of data collection which share coordinated actions, such as sampling strategies and protocols or inter-calibration, data dissemination and quality control, or data aggregation and archiving.

Whilst providing a broader high-level overview of needs, this document aims to identify those in situ observation types which can be carried out at high observation frequency, as these have the ability to focus cal/val efforts and can provide rapid return on investment. High-frequency observations are defined as being recorded at sufficiently short intervals to capture temporal variability within the timescales at which underlying processes are expected to vary, or alternatively, observations carried out at sufficiently short intervals to capture spatial variability whilst the observation platform and/or the observed water mass is moving.

Recommendations made in this report consider appropriate site selection, sampling intervals, reporting latency, maintenance considerations and instrument types. The main findings on the type of observations required are, per theme:

- For water level, the most appropriate high-frequency in situ sensors for continuous automated monitoring are bottom pressure sensors. Along rivers, or where a jetty is accessible, a radar measuring distance to the water surface is also highly suitable.
- For water extent and volume, no continuous direct cal/val method is identified. However, using precise bathymetry (echosounders) and elevation mapping of the surrounding land (e.g. drones), the uncertainties in satellite derived products can be characterised, and calibration is further improved by combining these results with in situ water level gauges. To validate water discharge, the rating curve (water level versus discharge) needs to be assessed. This requires water level gauges as well as flow rate measurements.
- For water temperature, the preferred observation is the skin temperature obtained using infrared radiometry. Alternatively, subsurface temperature can be obtained using thermometers, or thermistor chains, for example deployed on buoys. It is desirable to include cloud cover (sky camera or a pyranometer separating diffuse and direct irradiance). For modelling the heating effect of water bodies, knowing the albedo or reflectance (optical radiometry) and the vertical diffuse attenuation (optical profiles) are considered useful.
- For biogeochemical observations, a wide range of instrumentation may be considered. Hyperspectral reflectance validates the optical bottom-of-atmosphere satellite product from which other properties are derived and automated solutions are available. Site selection is of particular importance when recording reflectance, either to avoid land influence or to include it in characterisation of uncertainties. Absorption and (back)scattering are highly desirable additions which can be automated but require frequent maintenance of the in-water instruments. Combined with water sample analysis to determine concentration and weight of optical components, a set of in situ observations can be provided to aid in the calibration of biogeochemical retrieval algorithms and models.

The design of observation network nodes further includes considerations for the efficient dissemination of results at various levels of data processing. Data producers should align with a community repository and their requirements to make the data compliant for wider sharing purposes. Where such a repository does not exist, the producer will need to adopt a structured data storage solution coupled with a standardised data service, and register the data with an existing data discovery service. This requires a higher level of expertise than might be available with small-scale data providers. Thus, further community coordination is required.

2 Introduction

2.1 Objectives

The overarching objective of this document is to define an initial standard-of-practice (SOP) for in situ networked site operations to ensure competence in observations of the aquatic environment for monitoring and management up to the global scale. This requires that in situ and satellite observations as well as modelling efforts can be integrated despite operating across a wide range of spatial and temporal scales. An important part of this integration is to ensure high-quality in situ observations, to serve as statistical reference to model or algorithm performance. This intended scope guides the initial selection of observed variables (or ‘measurands’ in metrology). Other considerations to increase the impact of in situ data collections include appropriate site selection, traceable sensor calibration, and transparent data formatting, data aggregation and dissemination methods to optimise the impact from in situ observation collection efforts. This document highlights which key variables are suitable and relevant to be collected at high frequency to increase the number of observations coincident with satellite overpasses, in addition to those which can only be collected through dedicated field campaigns. The analysis is split over key observation and modelling domains of the cryosphere, water cycle, and biogeochemistry.

The key audience for this document consists of present and future site operators and monitoring agencies seeking to invest in closer synergy between the observation and modelling domains. This document does not detail operating standards or protocols, but does contain links to communities of practice and suitable instrumentation where these are identified.

Finally, we describe the minimum requirements and a recommended standard for data dissemination. This is to encourage observation nodes to form networks built on interoperable data standards, as well as to identify potential gaps in existing data collection networks.

Through other outputs of Water-ForCE Work Package 4 (WP4), recommendations are being provided regarding the use of metadata and introduction of new vocabulary into harmonised data collection systems. We also note a concurrent activity with GEO Aquawatch to recommend community-vetted nomenclature.

As a result of this SOP and the additional recommendations resulting from WP4, aquatic environmental observation networks will benefit from (1) comparable in situ data and satellite observation data (avoiding mismatch), (2) a coordinated strategy for sampling, deployment, and data reduction, and (3) sustainable efforts through tracing the impact of in situ observation operations.

The combined recommendations from WP4, particularly where gaps exist, will feed into a common Roadmap for the future of water related Copernicus services during 2023.

2.2 Definitions

2.2.1 Observation networks

Global-scale observation of the environment has become feasible through joined-up international research efforts, Earth observing satellite constellations, and vastly increased computational ability, during the last decades. Global-scale observations, combined with large-scale modelling, have informed policy about threats to global ecosystem health from pollution and climate change. This, in turn, has led researchers across science and industry to pursue collections of legacy observation time-series for model validation as well as higher-resolution observation strategies to observe subtle change in environmental trends. There is, therefore, a growing need for harmonised data collection, descriptions, storage and sharing facilities.

The need to curate data describing the physical environment resulted in custodial roles of international organisations, such as the World Meteorological Organization (WMO), for relevant collections of environmental observation data which also include aquatic ecosystems. The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) have further

highlighted the need for, and large gaps in, data collection to evidence progress towards these goals. Research to understand and mitigate climate change and changing weather patterns has placed particular emphasis on harmonised data collections of the physical properties of the environment. In comparison, biological and (bio)geochemical properties of aquatic ecosystems have seen data custodianship rise in response to the need to monitor progress towards the SDGs, notably SDG6 (“clean water and sanitation for all”) and SDG14 (“life below water”) and their specific indicators to describe catchment, ambient water quality properties and pollution.

“Observation networks” can be defined in the information age as nodes involved in the collection of data at multiple locations, through coordinated actions. International efforts to create and maintain community networks exist across the domains of meteorology and environmental observation.

Networks can also be interpreted to refer to flows of data between observation, ingestion, and processing nodes and between data producers and consumers. The scope of this SOP includes the cross-section of these network definitions. Data generated by a sensor are only meaningful if the context of data collection can be understood elsewhere in the network, and the data can be interpreted without ambiguity. Observation nodes are thus considered to be part of a network if they fulfil the following (minimal) conditions:

- They collect data with some intention of data dissemination and sharing.
- They consist of stable or moving data collection points such as buoys, ships, individuals, or community groups.
- They provide a flow of data which can be periodic or (semi)continuous.
- New observations are uniquely identifiable within the network.
- The purpose, and any limitations to use of the data collected by the node, are identifiable between network nodes.

For the purposes of integrated environmental observations from multiple sources, it is useful to prescribe additional conditions:

- Data can be traced back to their source throughout processing levels
- Data reduction and losses (quality control) can be determined at each processing level.
- Data are not held up by manual interventions other than system maintenance. This implies that observations which are manually collected or buffered at source, only become part of a network once they are entered into a common data flow.
- Processing to higher levels is triggered by the arrival of new data at lower processing levels.
- Quality control and calibration are part of the design of the network node.

2.2.2 High-frequency observations

Definitions:

- Observations of a measurand recorded at sufficiently short intervals to capture temporal variability within the timescales at which underlying processes are expected to vary.
- Alternatively, observations carried out at sufficiently short intervals to capture spatial variability whilst the observation platform and/or the observed water mass is moving.

Examples:

- Pigment auto-fluorescence observed at intervals of 1 second to describe vertical photochemical quenching at the minute-scale.
- Pigment auto-fluorescence observed at intervals of 1 minute to describe vertical migration of cells in 15-minute intervals.

- Water-leaving radiance along the track of a vessel moving at 10 knots (5.1 m s^{-1}) recorded at 10-second intervals to obtain up to five observations of remote-sensing reflectance within a single pixel of a medium resolution (270 m) ocean colour satellite sensor.

2.2.3 Metrology

This section provides an overview of common metrological definitions as they would be used to describe signals measured at high frequency.

Measurand: A physical property subject to measurement, e.g. air temperature.

Measurement: The act and result of quantifying a measurand.

Signal: Detector output (typically a current, voltage or pulse frequency)

Integration interval: Period over which a signal is sampled to obtain a single measurement or observation.

Measurement or observation: Representation of the measurand at a point in space and time, ideally described as the centre of the integration interval.

Calibration: Conversion of detector output to geophysical units, ideally traceable to laboratory standard conditions.

Characterization (of a Sensor, instrument, detector): the act of describing the instrument response in relation to changes in ambient conditions, e.g. temperature, pressure, contributing to the instrument calibration profile.

Error: Deviation of a measurement from the true value of the observed phenomenon. The magnitude of the error is typically unknown and not measurable but can be expressed theoretically.

Uncertainty: Expression of the known or probable magnitude of the error, by comparing observations to expectations, models, or through statistical analysis.

2.2.4 Signal processing

Signal processing levels typically used in geophysical sciences are based on the following base classification:

Level 0:	Uncalibrated signals
Level 1:	Calibrated signals (samples) at the native resolution of the detector
Level 2:	Interpreted samples
Level 3:	Spatio-temporally aggregated observations
Level 4:	Derived products

Processing to higher levels is typically irreversible, with the exception of some geometric conversions, e.g. linear scaling and offset corrections. It is, therefore, important to consider at which processing level data may have value for future applications before destroying low-level data. For example, reprocessing from Level 0 (L0) to Level 1 (L1) may be desirable when changes in the detector response over time have been determined.

The expression 'higher-level products' typically refers to processing Levels 3-4, for example:

- Seasonally aggregated concentration of chlorophyll-*a* as a proxy of trophic state
- Nutrient concentrations inferred from models that couple sediment load to chemical water properties (sometimes referred to as *virtual sensing*)

2.2.5 Data reduction principles

Data reduction is a fundamental process to efficiently collect, record and store observation data. Reduction can take place at each processing level and is non-reversible. It is, therefore, important in the design of an observation platform to consider how the relation between observation data and the measurand is changed with each reduction and the order in which

they take place, how the effects of data reduction can be captured, and what information should be relayed to data users to make them aware of the procedure that was followed.

To preserve data veracity through the various stages of signal processing, instrument manufacturers and sensor operators should ideally observe that:

- Signal calibration and quality control take place before signal aggregation.
- Sensors should be set to suitable integration intervals to obtain a meaningful signal-to-noise ratio, prior to sample aggregation.
- Integration intervals (to obtain individual samples) and aggregation intervals (combining multiple samples) should be stored with the observation records. Combined with the velocity of movement of the sampling platform or the target, this allows observations to be associated with a specific sampling distance or volume.
- When aggregating values, the method should be clearly communicated to users. For example, the variable name and/or a metadata property should indicate whether the geometric mean, median, another percentile function, etc., has been applied. Ideally, the variability within the sample population for which the aggregate statistic is provided, is also provided, alongside an indication of sample size. For example, information to be considered include
 - Geometric mean of sample population
 - Standard deviation of sample population
 - Number of samples in population
 - Time interval or distance over which sample population was aggregated
- Aggregated values of sample populations do not need to be mutually exclusive. For example, a moving average is an acceptable output if sufficient information on the sample population is provided so that users are later able to isolate separate sample populations.

3 Recommended variables to validate satellite observations and models

The thematic domains below provide an overview of recommended in situ observed variables and techniques to support their counterparts in satellite observation and modelling. Each domain focuses on the intersection of observation technologies and models. This information is intended for reference when planning or upgrading observation stations and field campaigns. To ensure a complete overview, the variables listed below are not necessarily observable with high-frequency observation strategies.

3.1 Water level, extent and volume

Satellite components: Altimetry, optical, synthetic aperture radar.

Model components: Hydrological models.

In situ reference: Bathymetry (sonar)

Water level referenced to geoid and bottom (precision geolocation, calibrated accelerometer, radar, or pressure at bottom).

Precision geolocation (D-GPS, RTK GPS) to trace water extent.

Where relevant, observations are referenced to tide (e.g. lagoons, estuaries), typically concentrated in the hours around high tide.

3.2 Water temperature

Satellite components: Thermal (skin temperature)

Model components: Layer temperature, vertical mixing (temperature stratification), evaporation, heat trapping, biogeochemical rates

In situ reference: Skin temperature (thermal infrared radiometry)

Subsurface temperature as function of depth bins (thermometers, thermistor chains)

Profiling across gradients (single thermometer, thermistor, CTD instruments)

Cloud cover during satellite overpass (sky camera)

Albedo or reflectance (optical radiometry)

Vertical diffuse attenuation (optical profiles)

3.3 (Optical) biogeochemistry

Satellite components: Optical (visible, near infrared, shortwave infrared reflectance).

Model components: Biogeochemical components and fluxes, food-web modelling, coupled hydrological-biogeochemical modelling of nutrient export, primary production, respiration, internal loading, oxygen dynamics.

In situ reference: Hydrologic optics:

Hyperspectral (ir)radiance, reflectance (in or above-water radiometry)

Bulk and/or partitioned light absorption (spectrophotometry)

Light (back)scattering

Light availability (vertical diffuse attenuation profiles)

Transparency (Secchi depth)

Turbidity, inorganic/organic suspended solids dry weight

Trophic levels, population dynamics:

Phytoplankton chlorophyll-a pigment concentration (analysis of extracts, in vivo absorption and/or fluorescence)

Accessory photosynthetic and photoprotective pigments
(analysis of extracts, in vivo fluorescence)

Phytoplankton group abundance/biomass (microscopy,
flow-cytometry, imaging)

Phytoplankton functional groups (microscopy, pigments,
imaging)

Zooplankton abundance/biomass (microscopy, optical or
laser optical counters, imaging)

Biofilms (microscopy, pigments, imaging)

Rooted/floating vegetation cover (imaging)

Primary production, eutrophication, trophic state, habitats:

Dissolved inorganic nutrient concentration (wet chemistry /
optics)

Primary productivity (analytical, single-turnover
fluorescence) and/or gross/net primary production (C
fixation, oxygen evolution)

Light availability (vertical diffuse attenuation profiles,
transparency)

4 General requirements for satellite cal/val

In situ reference observation requirements depend on the purpose for which they are used as reference. In broad terms, we may consider satellite product calibration/validation versus satellite product uncertainty characterization. When the purpose of in situ data collection is

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to compare the performance of multiple algorithms, some requirements for data quality or temporal matching may be relaxed compared to studies aiming to characterise product uncertainty.

The requirements for satellite product calibration versus validation are generally the same. Inaccurate algorithm calibration against in situ observation would result in proportional validation metrics in the absence of observation bias, so they are equivalent. It is best, therefore, to speak of calibration to a reference uncertainty (e.g. 10%), meaning that the reference (in situ) value has a known (average) uncertainty associated with it, and satellite product validation must then fall within this known uncertainty to be 'valid to within 10%'.

To know the reference uncertainty, calibration of in situ instrumentation and characterization of the result observations are required. The instrument calibration needs to be traceable to a trusted standard, whilst random effects on uncertainty (e.g. environmental variability) can be expressed through repeat observations. The calibration history of the in situ reference systems should be accessible at the point of use. Increasingly, research communities recommend that a subset of observation nodes are maintained to Fiducial Reference Measurement (FRM) standards. To meet the FRM requirements, an observation must:

- Document evidence of traceability to the international system of units (SI)
- Be independent from the satellite geophysical retrieval process
- Detail an uncertainty budget for the instrumentation and measurement process for the range of conditions it is used over.
- Adhere to community agreed measurement protocols and management practices.

To characterise satellite product uncertainties, additional information may be required, depending how the uncertainties are expressed and whether they are propagated through each stage of data processing or assessed only on the final product. For example, to propagate uncertainty for chlorophyll-a products, we need to determine the satellite sensor radiometric uncertainty, as well as atmospheric correction and chlorophyll-a algorithm uncertainty.

For purposes of satellite validation, the time and spatial windows between in situ and remote observation need to be kept narrow due to environmental variability in atmospheric and ground conditions. This requires additional information on the placement and synchronisation of the sensors to be provided.

The operator of in situ instrumentation is required, in summary, to provide the following ancillary and metadata to the observations:

- Sensor calibration that was applied
- Sensor description (manufacturer, model)
- Unaggregated (no interpolation or averaging) calibrated sensor readings
- Optionally, aggregated data (e.g. average and variability over specific time period)
- Sensor location (coordinates and projection/datum/geoid)
- Location source (e.g. Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) or manual/map)
- Sensor height above target, if relevant
- Timestamp with each sample
- Time source for the timestamp (e.g. GNSS, internet time pool)
- A description of the installation location in English
- A description of the platform (buoy, mast, raft, etc)
- The viewing direction and/or depth of the reading
- Contact details (email address) of the instrument operator, data owner and metadata provider.
- Unique identifiers for sampling platform, instrument, dataset or deployment, and any calibrations applied, to support traceability and to aid deduplication of records.

5 Recommended deployments for in situ networks and nodes for the Copernicus ‘water’ services

This section provides considerations for thematic in situ observation activities with particular focus on high-volume and/or high-frequency observations, provided by remote sensing experts in the respective domains. Key elements included below are:

- Site selection
- Sampling intervals
- Latency
- Maintenance
- Suitable instruments or sensor types

Sampling protocols are not part of this assessment.

5.1 Water level, extent and volume

5.1.1 Water level

For water level using altimetry as the satellite component, major challenges are encountered particularly in inland waters. Here, the in situ reference is the water level from a limnigraph, which may include fixed rulers, pressure sensors at the water bottom, radar observation or position of a buoy. The water level is referenced to the geoid.

Besides comparing water level from in situ gauges to satellite altimetry, potential biases between altimeters need to be assessed as part of satellite cal/val. These biases consist of electromagnetic bias and internal instrument biases.

The water level estimated from satellite altimetry further depends on tropospheric corrections, which require specific validation. Reference measurements for these include GNSS signal reception (atmospheric delay) and weather stations to measure in situ atmospheric pressure. Biases are also measured from field campaigns, using GNSS kinematic level measurements along the satellite tracks.

Site selection: the performance of altimetry to determine water level depends on the size of the lakes or river. To determine altimeter biases, relatively large lakes are preferred, as satellite tracks are most likely to meet within a short time period, avoiding significant spatio-

temporal water level change during the assessment period. For validation of the water level product, it is desirable to sample a large number of lakes representing different conditions (for example, tropical and mountain regions may affect the quality of measurements). Particularly for rivers, in situ gauges should be positioned as close as possible to the intersection of the satellite track with the river.

Sampling interval: daily sampling is sufficient for lakes because daily variability in water level tends to be lower than the expected accuracy of the satellite product. Automated sensors (like radar or bottom pressure) should nevertheless sample hourly to characterise this variability. Some reference observations can only be obtained during field campaigns, such as calibration of altimetry corrections whilst avoiding wind effects and sampling along the altimeter track. Field campaigns can be done using GNSS on a boat or drone (increasingly used over rivers).

Latency: In situ data latency up to a few days is largely sufficient.

Maintenance: in situ gauges can present drift either in the sensors used or from a failing installation. Annual levelling using GNSS measurements as the reference is recommended. Security can also be an issue, with local site support recommended to control gauges regularly, checking for damage.

Instruments: the most suitable sensors for continuous automated monitoring are bottom pressure sensors. Along rivers, or where a jetty is accessible, a radar measuring distance to the water surface is also highly suitable (e.g. OTT RLS or VORTEX microstations). For field campaigns and quality control, GNSS observations are the best reference, and receivers can be installed on boats, buoys and drones.

Figure 1: Methods for water level extent and volume mapping are mostly based in field campaigns. Image credits: team SWOT Nord Este FUNCEME/IRD/CPRM/CNES.

5.1.2 Water extent and volume

It is generally not possible to have continuous monitoring of the extent and volume of surface water bodies or width of rivers. However, using precise bathymetry (water depth) and elevation mapping (for the surrounding land), the uncertainties in satellite derived products can be determined with sufficient accuracy. To fully calibrate the satellite product, these procedures should be matched with in situ gauges of the water level. Finally, to validate water discharge, the rating curve (water level versus discharge) needs to be assessed. This requires water level gauges as well as flow rate measurements.

Instruments: Bathymetry is obtained using echosounders. Elevation can be mapped using drones equipped with altimeters and precise GNSS positioning or more traditional slope measurements if landscape morphology allows. The extent of a water body at a given time

can be mapped using geolocation methods, whilst tracing the shoreline either on land or from a boat or kayak. Flow rate can be measured using acoustic Doppler current profilers (ADCP).

5.2 Water temperature

The core, preferred variable to observe in situ is the skin temperature obtained using infrared radiometry. Alternatively, subsurface temperature can be obtained using thermometers, or thermistor chains, for example deployed on buoys. To characterise the observation environment, recording cloud cover (e.g. with a sky camera or a pyranometer capable of separating diffuse and direct irradiance) is useful to determine which of the high-frequency observations are useful for comparison against simultaneous satellite overpasses. Finally, for modelling the heating effect of water bodies, knowing the albedo or reflectance (optical radiometry) and the vertical diffuse attenuation (optical profiles) are considered useful.

Sites: for calibration and validation, consider the satellite sensors of interest and position the reference observation station away from islands and coast by at least one edge of swath pixel, if possible. Avoid inflows causing temperature gradients. For lakes, the centre or wherever the distance to land is largest, is best. Although high-resolution thermal sensors exist on some satellite platforms (Landsat 8/9, ASTER TIR) with 90-100m resolution, the majority of observations used in climate studies come from coarser sensors with approximately 1-km ground resolution. Thus, stations positioned >1 km from shore are preferred.

Intervals: at least hourly averages of 1-s measurements over 5 min intervals is a strategy used for Sea Surface Temperature (SST) buoys, and which would meet requirements also for inland water systems. If power consumption is not a concern, 5 min averages is recommended.

Latency: most current data sources are not online and have effectively an annual latency. Bringing data online through standardised services would be a major improvement, and

reducing latency of quality-controlled data to within a few days (< 10) would be a huge advance.

Maintenance: clean fouling, secure from theft and vandalism. Calibration drift and maintenance should include pre-deployment calibration as well as cross-calibration activities of deployed systems. Removable buoy sensors have the advantage of being easier to include in manufacturer-independent laboratory assessments to avoid bias. Buoys deployed in seas and oceans have long been considered impossible to recover for recalibration due to the cost and effort involved in recovery, but in coastal and inland settings, annual recalibration is feasible.

Instruments: The Ships4SST project operates shipborne radiometers which include the Infrared Sea surface temperature Autonomous Radiometer (ISAR) used on various vessels, and the Scanning Infrared Sea surface Temperature Radiometer (SISTeR). Further specifications, including for buoys, are available from (1) EUMETSAT fiducial reference measurement programme (FRM4STS), and/or (2) the Global Drifter Programme (Scripps) with sensors positioned 15 cm below the water surface (<https://www.aoml.noaa.gov/global-drifter-program/>).

5.3 (Optical) biogeochemistry

In most cases, the largest satellite product uncertainties relate to the process of atmospheric correction of satellite data, particularly near land. To address these uncertainties requires in situ radiometric variables to be observed: the below-surface up- and downwelling (ir)radiance extrapolated to zero-depth, or the above-water downwelling irradiance, water-leaving radiance and sky radiance. Detailed measurement protocols are available, for example in the recently revised IOCCG Protocol Series (2019)¹ on in situ optical radiometry.

¹ IOCCG Protocol Series (2019). Protocols for Satellite Ocean Colour Data Validation: In Situ Optical Radiometry. Zibordi, G., Voss, K. J., Johnson, B. C. and Mueller, J. L. IOCCG Ocean Optics and

For inland and coastal waters in particular, optical diversity is large due to the uncoupled nature of optical water constituents, broadly partitioned into Coloured Dissolved Organic Matter (CDOM), phytoplankton pigments, the unpigmented part of cells, mineral particles and detritus. Optical partitioning to determine light absorption characteristics is possible by filtration of water samples and subsequent analysis in spectrophotometers, for which in situ and laboratory instruments exist. Very few in situ spectrophotometers can be operated for long periods of time without consistent (in the order of daily) maintenance, although some exist in depth profiling systems which limit the time that instruments are exposed to water (see instruments, below). Absorption of bulk light absorption combined with light backscattering or volume scattering over multiple angles is useful, to determine whether satellite-based algorithms can translate reflectance into the bulk absorption and backscattering properties upon which many biogeochemical retrieval algorithms (e.g. for chlorophyll-a or total suspended matter) are based. Further differentiating the absorption coefficient into dissolved and particulate fractions is of superior value because this allows validation of so-called physics-based algorithms for the retrieval of specific water constituents from optical remote sensing. Dissolved and particulate fractions may be obtained using cross-flow filtration coupled to field spectrometers, which requires significant maintenance effort. Differentiation into organic and mineral components, phytoplankton pigment versus particulate fractions is not readily achieved in field deployment. The standard for this differentiation is achieved in the laboratory using dual-beam spectrophotometry on glass-fibre filters positioned inside a 150-mm integrating sphere.

Light availability at depth is an important variable for primary production modelling, which can be estimated from optical satellite sensors. In situ, this requires depth profiling to obtain the vertical diffuse attenuation coefficient either as the broadband Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR, 400-700 nm) or in discrete wavebands, where 490 nm is often

Biogeochemistry Protocols for Satellite Ocean Colour Sensor Validation, Volume 3.0, IOCCG, Dartmouth, NS, Canada. <http://dx.doi.org/10.25607/OBP-691>

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considered a close approximation of PAR in coastal and ocean waters, whilst multi- or hyperspectral observations are preferable in optically more diverse inland water bodies. Relatedly, transparency and turbidity estimates can be obtained, with turbidity preferred for high-frequency observations because affordable optical sensors are readily available.

Within the context of primary production and eutrophication estimates, the concentration of the main phytoplankton pigment chlorophyll-a can be approximated in situ from absorption measurements or fluorescence. The fluorescence of phycobilipigments which are somewhat diagnostic of cyanobacteria, can also be targeted using in situ fluoroprobes. The fluorescence yield is subject to variability related to phytoplankton taxonomic composition, light and nutrient history, and therefore usually not preferred as reference observation to pigment concentration estimates from remote sensing. Here, it is useful to note that the remote sensing estimate is typically based on light absorption properties, as opposed to the more variable in vivo fluorescence. Advanced fluorescence methods to determine the efficiency of energy transfer from light absorption by pigments through photosystem II are designed to quantify photochemistry and may be used in reference to models of primary production, even with remotely sensed inputs. Solutions exist in the form of submersible and benchtop units (including some fully sealed designs suitable for external deployment).

Phytoplankton and zooplankton size distributions, taxonomic breakdown and/or functional grouping have significant value in the calibration and validation of biogeochemical models. For satellite product validation, global approaches to estimate phytoplankton size and/or functional groups tend to be mostly used in the open ocean. Options for automation of phytoplankton and zooplankton monitoring include flow cytometers and imaging of individual particles. Artificial Intelligence based methods to subsequently classify the results into plankton taxonomic or functional groups are steadily gaining ground to further enable automation.

Sites: for strict calibration and validation, position the reference observation station near the location of the maximum distance from land (for round lakes, this would be the centre). This

will allow product validation in a 'best-case' scenario because satellite product uncertainties tend to increase towards the coast due to mixing of land/water signals in the atmosphere. To characterise this 'adjacency effect', observations along transects with spatial sampling intervals at the sub-pixel scale, are very useful and may be obtained from boats, ships-of-opportunity, or drones.

Locations where water masses are generally stable will be most useful to determine long-term drift in water quality (e.g. climate studies) whilst also contributing to satellite product calibration and validation. Sites having a more dynamic nature also have considerable value, as these provide a wider range of optical properties such that algorithms can be tested over a wider range in a shorter period.

For all passive radiometric observations, positioning sensors to avoid sunglint is essential. This includes deployment on drones where the flight plan and sensor orientation should accommodate sunglint avoidance, static observation platforms along the most suitable stretch of shoreline, and ship based deployment requiring adjustment of viewing geometries for both sun azimuth and ship heading.

Intervals: the shortest possible time-difference with satellite overpasses should be attempted, whilst for model calibration and validation it is important to capture the diurnal variability of biological components, to validate biogeochemical models. Most optical instruments for the listed variables can be completed within 1 second (by order-of-magnitude). Depending on the exact implementation, e.g. whether instruments need flushing out or not, they may be repeated as many times as feasible in 5-10 minute intervals. Radiometric observations should always be provided as single (non-aggregated) observations because light field fluctuations between measurements tend to include glint, which propagates towards the reflectance product as positive bias. Other observations (absorption, fluorescence, backscattering) tend to use active light sources and are therefore controlled and more stable with regard to ambient light field fluctuations. These observations may be aggregated, reporting elements of the value distribution (average and standard deviation, or percentiles, start time and duration of the sequence).

Due to periodic cloud cover, the time window of measurements should be at least several hours around the satellite overpass window, so that the volume of ‘matchups’ may be increased as a function of window size, generating additional data points outside clear sky conditions. This is important, because biological components may respond in diverse ways to light conditions and excluding (partially) overcast conditions could lead to clear-weather bias in the calibration of algorithms. It is, therefore, advisable to include at least some radiometric components into in situ observation stations to describe the intensity of the downwelling light field. Even a broadband (PAR) sensor for downwelling light can accomplish this, by comparing the observed intensity of downwelling light to that of a modelled clear sky for the site location.

Latency: it is advisable to implement a degree of automated quality control to flag issues with incoming data early, before the data are released for wider purposes. Bringing data online through standardised services is highly encouraged, including quality control flags as relevant. The latency of quality-controlled data is ideally within a few days (< 10) from observation.

Maintenance: clean fouling, secure from theft and vandalism. Requirements very much depend on exposure to weather and vicinity to land. Operators should determine the appropriate cleaning regime for their site, adapting to seasonal change. Calibration drift, particularly for passive light sensors, should be monitored as advised through the relevant protocols, advice from the manufacturer, and observing the traceability standards for Fiducial Reference Measurements (see previous chapter). For radiometric observations, annual calibration is highly recommended, particularly after the first year when optics may change more quickly.

Instruments: there are several manufacturers of submersible in situ optical equipment, ranging from single sensors which require integration into a platform supplying power and connectivity, to fully integrated profiling solutions. A useful overview of sensors for some commonly considered biogeochemical variables (oxygen, pH, nutrients, etc) in relatively

low-cost deployment is available from the NETLAKE Guidelines for automatic monitoring station development².

The bulk inherent optical properties (light absorption and (back)scattering) can be observed hyperspectrally using a combination of Wetlabs AC-S and backscatterometers, either in submerged or flowthrough mode. Alternatives for the bulk absorption coefficient use flow-through integrating spheres. Open-path spectrometer designs can be used to obtain the beam attenuation coefficient, but this has considerably lower value in satellite or model product comparison than light absorption and scattering designs.

For hyperspectral reflectance, drifter, profiler and buoy solutions exist but all require very regular maintenance, secure solutions and corrections for self-shading which require simultaneous knowledge of the light absorption coefficient. For automated above-water spectroradiometry from fixed locations (jetties, masts), dedicated solutions exist in the form of the Water Insight WISPstation and HYPstar (expected in 2023). For moving platforms (ships, large buoys), the open-source So-Rad automation solution for TriOS RAMSES may be considered, whilst commercial alternatives include the ISMO DALEC, and Sea-Bird HyperSAS (discontinued). Solutions for mounting sensors on drones have come to market in recent years. For considerations, please see the MONOCLE factsheet on Drones³.

² Laas, A, Pierson, D., de Eyto, E. and Jennings, E. 2016. Sensor considerations (Factsheet 009). In: Laas, A, de Eyto, E, Pierson, D. and Jennings, E. (Eds.) NETLAKE Guidelines for automatic monitoring station development. Technical report. NETLAKE COST Action ES1201. pp 37-39. <https://research.thea.ie/handle/20.500.12065/1939>.

³ https://monocle-h2020.eu/Project_Resources

6 Data dissemination

This section addresses some of the common issues facing data providers (items 1, 2 & 3 in Figure 2). The processing networks described in section 2.2.1 should already be configured to automatically process data and metadata:

- Data are collected with some intention of data dissemination and sharing.
- The flow of data is periodic or (semi)continuous.
- Observations are uniquely identifiable within the network.
- Data processing is predominantly automated.

If these conditions are met, the final stage of any processing converts data to a publishable format and makes it available via some form of (ideally Interoperable) data service. It may further be desirable to publish data at different processing levels (near real time/not quality controlled, individual observations, or aggregated).

Although the data publishing process can be automated, it can require considerable technical expertise depending on the services provided. For this reason, all except the largest data producing organisations should prefer to submit data to a relevant repository rather than providing a data service of their own. This submission can still be automated.

Implementing solutions for the above conditions helps to meet the FAIR concept (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), in particular the Findability and Interoperability criteria. For a detailed discussion on how all FAIR conditions should be achieved, please refer to Water-Force report D4.6 “Guidelines to enable interoperability of in-situ networks and connection with GEOSS”.

To be useful, a repository should:

- Provide clear data submission guidelines regarding:
 - Data formatting.
 - Metadata requirements.

- Any restrictions on data submitted such as maximum size, measurement, location of measurement.
- Provide simple interfaces for data ingestion to the repository, via a defined API if possible.
- Facilitate the generation of DOIs.
- Provide discovery metadata and ensure this is published to relevant discovery portals.
- Provide documented data access methods, preferably by API.
- Provide technical support to data providers and users.

Figure 2: Schematic showing the database characteristics considered in this report and the process from data providers to the end data users.

WaterForCE report D4.3 reports and makes recommendations on the storage of in situ data. It provides a list of existing repositories and gives some recommendations on future

direction. If it is possible to use one of the repositories identified then this will reduce the ongoing maintenance overhead associated with long term data storage. As discussed in D4.3, many repositories are quite specific in their holdings at present, however others, such as Zenodo, have a wide subject and geographical coverage as well as documented APIs for data upload and access.

If there is a requirement to maintain a local repository and data service then the following sections will provide guidance on the tools that may be used.

Even if the data are held locally, it is important that they are visible to the community; for this reason, it is recommended that discovery metadata is uploaded to relevant registries or a discovery service (CSW) is implemented as well as the data service. Discovery services should support standards such as INSPIRE [<https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/>] that allow geospatial data to be shared across wide communities.

Examples of good practice may be taken from related subject areas. For instance, MEDIN provides a discovery service for marine environmental data. The MEDIN Discovery Metadata Standard⁴ provides a useful example which translates well to the water community and is INSPIRE compliant. GEOSS sets out a general set of data management principles⁵.

6.1 Data storage

Data are frequently collected in varied file formats (frequently comma-separated value (CSV) files of some description). It is important that these data are stored in a structured format that enables easy filtering by location and time as well as providing a stable and reliable platform, such as consistently handling missing values.

The typical file format (e.g. CSV) is not well suited to integrating with geotemporal search facilities as the time and location will not necessarily be encoded in a machine usable

⁴ <https://medin.org.uk/medin-discovery-metadata-standard>

⁵ https://www.earthobservations.org/documents/dswq/201504_data_management_principles_long_final.pdf

format. The time component will often be encoded in the file name and the location either embedded in the CSV or, if all the data refers to a single location, encoded in the file or directory name. Whilst a strictly maintained directory structure could be used to support search capabilities a more structured format, such as a geospatially enabled database, will integrate better with dissemination services. Geospatial extensions are available for SQL databases such as PostgreSQL and MySQL/MariaDB as well as NoSQL databases, MongoDB and Elasticsearch.

PostgreSQL [<https://www.postgresql.org/>] is a fully featured object-relational database. When combined with the PostGIS extension [<https://postgis.net/>] it can provide all features necessary to act as a data source for any of the recommended data services. PostgreSQL has been established in geospatial processing for many years (PostGIS was first released in 2001) and supports a large number of standards and tools.

MySQL/MariaDB [<https://mariadb.org/>] is a fork of the MySQL [<https://www.mysql.com/>] relational database so both products have similar heritage in geospatial processing. Since the split the product development has diverged, with MySQL releasing version 8 in 2018 with enhanced geospatial capabilities. In 2016, MariaDB released version 10.2 which added GeoJSON processing and in 2022 they purchased CubeWerx, a geospatial data specialist. MySQL and MariaDB do not currently have the depth of support for geospatial processing provided by PostgreSQL/PostGIS.

MongoDB [<https://www.mongodb.com/home>] is a NoSQL database that supports GeoJSON. NoSQL databases are not as widely used in geospatial processing at present but, as geospatial and the wider web standards converge, are likely to be used and supported more widely.

ElasticSearch [<https://www.elastic.co/>] is another NoSQL database that supports GeoJSON. As for MongoDB, it can be integrated into geospatial processing using libraries such as GDAL/OGR.

6.2 Discovery Services

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To make collected and processed data discoverable by others, geospatial search and discovery is starting to adopt the same constructs as used in the wider web. **JSON-LD**, a lightweight linked data format, is increasingly being used to mark up web data pages (Structured data). **SpatioTemporal Asset Catalogs** (STAC) [<https://stacspec.org/en/>] provide a standardised way to expose spatiotemporal data and also use JSON, allowing easy integration into web search services. These new developments mean that searching for geotemporal data could become as simple as a standard web search. This is not currently the case so researchers looking for geotemporal data need to use well known portals that regularly “harvest” the databases holding the actual data.

For this reason, where possible, a community wide discovery service should be used. For example, the **Global Terrestrial Network – Hydrology** [<https://www.gtn-h.info/>] was set up “to make data from existing global hydrological observation networks available and enhance their value through integration” and it is developing a GTN-H discovery service, however this is not yet available. Global discovery portals such as the GEOSS Portal [<https://www.geoportal.org/community/guest/general-information>] make it easiest for non-specialist users to locate datasets and it is important that community based data and discovery services are discoverable through these global servers.

Where it is not possible to use an external registry then there are a number of servers available that can be deployed locally. Geonetwork [<https://geonetwork-opensource.org/>] is a full featured cataloguing service that can be configured to produce INSPIRE compliant metadata. Pycsw [<https://pycsw.org/>] is an alternative discovery metadata server but does not have a graphical user interface.

6.3 Data Service Standards

The data provided by high-frequency in situ networks are inherently geospatial (associated with a position) and temporal (it will have a time for which it is valid) and these properties are important to tie the in situ observations with satellite (or model) products. There are a number of well-established community standards which specify how geotemporal data can

be communicated and these should be used to ensure that users of the data can download and process it using standard tools.

The Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) has developed a number of standards that apply to both point and coverage data which have location and time attributes. The OGC **Web Feature Service (WFS)** [<https://www.ogc.org/standards/wfs>] is a mature protocol that allows data to be accessed by third party client software (for instance QGIS [<https://www.qgis.org>]). Other OGC services such as **Sensor Observation Service (SOS)** [<https://www.ogc.org/standards/sos>], **SensorThings API (STA)** [<https://www.ogc.org/standards/sensorthings>] are specifically aimed at working with sensor data while the new **OGC API - Features** [<https://ogcapi.ogc.org/features/>] standard provides access to feature information via the latest web API standards. Specific standards have been developed to describe time-series observations (TSML, [<https://www.ogc.org/standard/tsml/>]) and measurements of water variables (WaterML, [<https://www.ogc.org/standard/waterml/>]).

6.3.1 Web Feature Service

The OGC WFS is the most mature and general service listed. The WFS standard makes geographic feature data available through XML. By default, the data returned by a WFS is in Geography Markup Language (GML) which is written as eXtensible Markup Language (XML). WFS is agnostic about the data contained in each feature collection. However, version 2 of WFS provides support for both geospatial and temporal filters if the dimension data is well defined.

6.3.2 Sensor Observation Service and SensorThings API

In contrast to WFS, SOS and STA provide access to observations from sensors and sensor systems in a standard way that is consistent for all sensor systems including remote, in situ, fixed and mobile sensors.

The SensorThings API is designed specifically to enable the dissemination of observations from IoT devices and the Web and uses approaches that are considered lighter weight

(REST, JSON and the Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT)) while SOS uses the same XML/RPC approach as WFS. Finally, it should be noted that the standards are typically designed to transmit a single or simple set of observation data per feature. Complex data types (e.g. arrays, or multiple types per feature) are not as well supported.

6.3.3 OGC API - Features

The new OGC APIs are a Web 2.0 style reimplementation of the older OGC standards such as WFS. They provide a more modern API which is easier for developers to use. Pygeoapi [<https://pygeoapi.io/>] is the reference implementation for the OGC API - Features standard.

6.4 Suggested configurations

The following sections provide suggested configurations for setting up a local data service. This is not a definitive list and other combinations may work well in a specific instance.

6.4.1 PostgreSQL and Geoserver WFS

This is the most well established combination and there are many examples of its use. Geoserver [<https://geoserver.org/>] can be configured with an extension that provides INSPIRE compliant metadata⁶.

6.4.2 PostgreSQL and SensorThings API

The SensorThings API is more recent but provides a sensor specific and light weight service. It has been proposed as an INSPIRE data service⁷. FROST server⁸ is a STA implementation available in an easy to install Docker container.

6.4.3 MongoDB and Pygeoapi

⁶ <https://docs.geoserver.org/latest/en/user/extensions/inspire/index.html>

⁷ <https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/good-practice/ogc-sensorthings-api-inspire-download-service>

⁸ <https://github.com/FraunhoferIOSB/FROST-Server>

Pygeoapi [<https://pygeoapi.io/>] is the OGC reference implementation of the OGC API - Features standard. It supports a number of backend data stores (ElasticSearch, MongoDB, PostgreSQL). An example of using Pygeoapi to serve data from MongoDB is provided in the Pygeoapi GitHub repository⁹.

7 Conclusions and Recommendations

There are meaningful high-frequency additions possible in each of the investigated thematic domains to support the calibration and validation of satellite products and models. No major gaps are currently identified as regards selection of protocols, intercalibration methods, and quality control, because examples from dedicated research campaigns guided by existing protocols already exist. Instead, expansion of these efforts is the major improvement which is now needed. In situ observation, remote sensing and modelling communities should work together to identify sites which show the largest potential to fill current data gaps, in order to justify the required investment, in each of the discussed thematic domains.

Communication around common or reciprocal requirements between the in situ observation, remote sensing and modelling communities can be arranged through network coordination, such as already seen in, for example, GTN-H, GEMStat, Hydrolare, EMODNet, and RadCalNet. These do not presently cover the full requirements for satellite and model validation (see also Water-ForCE D4.3) and most offer limited functionality to bring in high-resolution observation data in near real-time, particularly with complex data types (e.g. reflectance or absorption spectra). This is a shortcoming where transferable situ methodology already exists to support network expansion, or where it is being developed. In other cases, such as the collection of water extent outlines, the manual collection and data dissemination effort is still acceptable because high frequency data collection is

⁹ <https://github.com/emotional-cities/pygeoapi/tree/mongo>

unlikely. For the Copernicus services, it is crucial to engage in the process to ensure their requirements are ultimately met. The role of Copernicus In Situ in developing harmonised standards and observation practices is not immediately clear, but there is a clear need to coordinate collection and sharing of high-frequency data, particularly where these fall outside the scope of the hydrological monitoring networks, which are largely organised under WMO activities.

The burden, in terms of time/cost and expertise required, of setting up data services and disseminating these through discovery services is significant. Technical support should be provided to ensure common standards are followed, to secure data for the future, and to make the data easily discoverable. As the standards evolve, the FAIR principles will be increasingly met, to the point that data discovery starts from a standard web search. However, this evolution requires investment into new and existing repositories and financial support for centralised, coordinating bodies to keep data records relevant.

